

A critical review of whole theory: Stationenlernen learning technique and German language learning outcomes

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ABSTRACT

This critical review aims to describe the integrity of paraphrasing the theory or references and scientific journals that become references. The contribution of this research is as a reference and input to develop the creativity of critical thinking of the quoters. The method used is listening and analyzing the journal's contents as a source of data; critically identifying the parts of the journal containing quotations, direct quotations, and paraphrasing of the theories being referenced. The results of the critical review show several weaknesses, including several quotes that are not accompanied by relevant data and references, errors in citing reference sources. In addition, quotations or paraphrases have paid attention to the integrity of meaning with several techniques, namely complete and partial paraphrasing techniques. Partial is divided into two; according to the research formulation, the theory is paraphrased and several points of the combined theory are paraphrased because they are closely related and complementary. This critical review implies that it is a follow-up study to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of a scientific article based on relevant theories, studies, and previous research results.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Higher-order thinking skills have special characters or characteristics, namely the ability to think critically and think creatively. Both of these abilities are needed by someone in writing an article. Brookhart discovered that higher order thinking skills (HOTS) have three meanings: transfer, critical thinking skills, and problem-solving techniques [1]. Critical thinking has a close relationship with the brain in solving problems [2]. In this case related to article writing because critical thinking and cognitive growth appear to be essential themes in higher education [3]. Critical thinking is characterized by a person's ability to analyze and consider things carefully, based on logic, before making decisions or conclusions. Regarding critical thinking, the importance of using and utilizing resources effectively is also very influential in scientific work. This can be done by critically distinguishing between our ideas and ideas from other sources. The issue that frequently emerges is that the papers that have been gathered have not followed the signs that should have been followed and tend to be clones of theories, sometimes with ambiguous references. There was one of the issues discovered that technology that makes it simple is frequently abused, leading writers to seek quick solutions, such as copying and moving compositions into articles while breaking the standards of proper and correct citation.

In writing scientific papers, every writer has a moral obligation to comply with all the scientific procedures undertaken, including avoiding plagiarism. Despite the anti-plagiarism software now in use, plagiarism can occur in any scientific journal [4]. In other words, every researcher or writer is prohibited from plagiarizing or taking the ideas, findings, or conclusions of other authors without citing the source because such behavior is categorized as a severe violation of the scientific world [5]. This idea is in line with Sukaesih's opinion that plagiarism is not only an act of harm to writers whose works are plagiarized, but also describes a lack of creativity that worsens the mentality of the perpetrators [6]. Plagiarism is a scientific disaster [7]. Plagiarism should be punished severely, and safeguards for whistleblowers should be put in place and enforced. As a result, bad and lazy authors who circumvent the system would be penalized, while good authors would be serviced [8]. When using words, ideas, or any information from other sources than knowledge and experience, must appreciate the owner of the quote by informing the source of the quote. If you don't give academic credit to the referenced section, it is called an act of plagiarism [9]. To avoid plagiarism, individual conduct relating to the author's duty and ethics in citing someone else's work is essential [10]. In addition, the author also avoids direct quotations without being processed as much as possible because these actions can also describe the author's low creativity or understanding of the theory referred to.

Therefore, every theory that becomes a reference needs to be paraphrased without changing the meaning of the idea or ideas quoted by the author's source. Paraphrasing should be done in its entirety, not only from the source side but also from the substance side. This opinion means that all elements in the theory of reference must be considered. Thus, two things need to be considered in paraphrasing: the integrity of the source and the integrity of the content. The integrity of the reference source describes the author's appreciation of the original author's ideas or thoughts. At the same time, the integrity of the content refers to the quoter's skill to appreciate the original author's ideas or ideas comprehensively while at the same time describing the critical thinking creativity of the quoter.

This critical review focuses on the two things namely, the integrity of the source and the integrity of the content or theories quoted by the author. With reference to the question of whether the theory cited refers to a clear source, as well as whether paraphrasing the theory describes or represents the theory being paraphrased. Or in other words, whether the paraphrase retains the material or aspects of the original theory as a whole.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

A qualitative research approach with a literature review was performed. A literature review refers to a written summary of journal articles, books, and other publications that provide historical and contemporary data relevant to the subject of a research project [11]. The literature review is used to criticize a scientific article, which analyzes the advantages and disadvantages of a scientific article based on relevant theories, studies, and previous research results. This research's critical review focuses on the integrity of the source and the integrity of the content or theories cited by the author.

The technique used in the critical review is to listen and analyze the contents of scientific articles as a data source. Critically identify parts of the article containing quotations, direct quotes, and paraphrases from the referenced theories. Then the sections are grouped, tabulated, and described about the original idea. The data source for this research is the scientific journal article by Litaly and Serpara [12]. In general, the purpose of this article is to determine if the use of the Stationenlernen learning strategy improves German learning results. Meanwhile, the study's precise objective was described, which was to assist students at State High School 1 (SMA Negeri 1) Saparua in Central Maluku Province, Indonesia in improving their low German learning outcomes.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This critical review aims to describe the integrity of paraphrasing the theory or references and scientific journals that become references. Based on the methods and techniques that have been applied to critical review the scientific article "Stationenlernen Learning Technique and German Language Learning Outcomes" it can be found that the article has used easy-to-understand language and coherent writing systematics. The data is presented in a table. That makes it easier for the reader to understand the content of the study. For each statistical test, the formula used is explained. Tables in the form of a summary of statistical test results are interpreted in detail. The interpretation of statistical test results is discussed and linked to supporting theories and relevant research results. It was also found that the quotations or paraphrases in this article have taken into account the integrity of the meaning or theory with two techniques, namely complete and partial paraphrasing techniques. Behind the advantages, of course, there are weaknesses

in this article. Relevant data and references do not accompany some theoretical citations. In addition, there are errors in citing reference sources.

3.1. Discussion of scientific articles

Based on a review of the subject matter of the scientific article, explained that the introductory section of the article presented the reasons for conducting the research. Because based on the existing theory, although understanding German is crucial, the outcomes of learning German in high school/vocational high school (SMA/SMK), particularly in Saparua (Central Maluku, Indonesia), have not been noteworthy. This condition is caused by a lack of acceptable learning material, which is complemented by the employment of appropriate German language learning procedures based on preliminary research team observations of student learning results.

The theoretical study also includes the most recent and relevant data on increasing student learning outcomes using Bloom's cognitive domain. The major source is emphasized, namely the notion of learning outcomes, which is a transformation in the individual. The planned transformation encompasses not just information but also abilities, attitudes, and comprehension. However, the article is also based on various theories. Furthermore, the report offered statistics on student learning outcomes based on the study team's early findings. Research reviews through preliminary observations help to determine the urgency of the article, namely the importance of learning German, therefore students in high school need to also improve learning outcomes in class through appropriate learning techniques that teachers can apply.

This article employs quasi-experimental research, in which the experiment is conducted on a single set of students with no comparison group. The article's summary indicates that the researcher used or experimented with the Stationenlernen learning strategy in the German language learning process in the hopes of helping students enhance the quality of their learning results when studying German. In addition, the research identifies the weaknesses, benefits, and areas for improvement in learning German.

3.2. Discussion of whole theory

Some of the theoretical citations that have been questioned in relation to the integrity of the theory stated and paraphrased by the author can be described; the first theory cited by the author is in Indonesia, German is taught as a Foreign language in high school as well as vocational school and university, indicating the critical importance of mastering the language [13]. The original theory is during this period, there were three main kinds of languages spoken in Indonesia: i) Regional or vernacular languages; ii) National languages (Indonesia languages); and iii) Foreign languages, such as English, German, and Arabic. [14], [15]. Mastering another language can be what Turner and Allen describe 'self-identity – a sense of knowing or belonging'. For Indonesian being able to speak a foreign language, they can be identified as a knowledgeable individual [16]. Criticisms for source integrity is the paraphrases in this discussion have quoted the source or reference in full. The quote paraphrased by the author does not fully represent the original two theories. This paraphrase emphasizes more on foreign languages taught in Indonesia but ignores the reasons for the importance of learning foreign languages, as stated by Turner and Allen. In other words, paraphrasing the theory should also mention the benefits of learning a foreign language as proposed by Turner and Allen.

The second theory paraphrased is about five important reasons to learn German [17]. These referenced sources are inaccurate. This fact means that no original theory is found. The author's second paragraph cites five reasons that German is an important language to learn in the world. However, no original theory was found against the referenced reference. Based on the data obtained, the reference is an e-book learning German, which discusses learning the German language and culture. The author tries to make conclusions from the materials and practice questions contained in the e-book to be paraphrased into five reasons why German is mandatory and important to learn. As input for the author, additional references and theories can be used from the ideas of Krumm which explains that in terms of the number of speakers, German is the language with the most significant number of speakers in the European Union region, which has the most substantial economic influence in the European Union. This power impacts eastern European countries, so that German is also studied because it provides economic benefits for every speaker [18].

Mastering German is important, but results of learning German in Saparua sub-district, have not improved significantly. As a result of the lack of adequate resources, German educational techniques are not being used. There is a need to apply appropriate media and learning techniques to improve and increase student learning achievement [19]–[21]. Criticisms for Source integrity is no original theory was found; the author referred to that because it took ideas or ideas from the results of previous research. The paraphrased quote is irrelevant to the research problem because the research results were used as a reference theory from Peters, Wartono & Nilasari, and Wickramanayake & Muhammad did not conduct their research in Central Maluku. It is recommended that the research results referred to are relevant to the locations mentioned, namely in Saparua, Central Maluku.

It is expected that the Stationenlernen learning technique will develop students' learning outcomes in German by being open, independent and interactive [22]. There are three original theories that are paraphrased by the author, namely: i) In terms of open instruction, stationenlernen can be applied to almost any field of study, including foreign languages [23]; ii) Stationenlernen's student-centered learning activities are creatively designed so that they can work more independently, intensely, efficiently, and at their own pace [23]; iii) The communicative environment created through Stationenlernen helps students to become creators and receivers of the meanings of the text [22]. Critics for Source integrity is based on the data obtained, there are two different sources of reference with the same author. The two references are quoted from three other original theories. Two theories are derived from a study entitled "Stationenlernen", and one idea from a study entitled "An Interactive Reading". But in the reference section, the author only cites one reference, so that the source is quoted incompletely. First theory is entirely paraphrased by the author because it explains that Stationenlernen is an open learning technique. This fact means that it can be applied to all fields, including in language learning. While second theory is not quoted in its entirety because it only takes one aspect relevant to the author's aims and objectives, namely about student-centered independent learning. The interactive element cited by the author in third theory, it is also adapted to the author's needs related to the Stationenlernen learning technique so that it is not quoted intact. Overall, the combination of the three theories has been quoted and paraphrased well by the author to become a concise and clear idea.

In order for Stationenlernen to be successful, teachers need to be supportive of it, especially students [24]. Reference sources did not find any theory relevant to the ideas that have been paraphrased. The paraphrased theory may be the result of the author's observations. Teachers are expected to be highly creative and aggressive when setting up or managing learning stations with all the necessary materials and when directing the flow of teaching and learning activities so that they go without stumbling blocks [25]. While the original theory is the ability to be creative as a teacher is crucial in the realm of education. By working with someone who is qualified and knowledgeable in their area, performing classroom action research, and reflecting on the strategies used in their classrooms, teachers are expected to assume the role of students and foster their own creativity [26]. The paraphrases in this discussion have quoted the source or reference in full. In this section, the theory is quoted and paraphrased by the author based on the teacher's creativity aspect. In summary, the author relates the research results relevant to the Stationenlernen learning problem and the creative abilities that an educator must possess. The theory is incompletely paraphrased. That is, the author only cites one aspect that is relevant to the research and then paraphrased it.

Students must be able to support teaching and learning activities by giving their time, effort, and thoughtful consideration. They must also be prepared to collaborate with other students in groups [27], [28]. The original theories are: i) To accomplish learning goals, the Jigsaw approach is one of the active learning methods. This method depends on good communication between students in a group, including well-organized study materials, clear learning objectives, and enough time; ii) Throughout the research project, students gave their complete cooperation and engagement in the group that was formed and committed to collaborative learning. The sources referred to have been quoted in their entirety, and the references are explicit. Based on these two theories, the writer quotes and paraphrases briefly and clearly to support the relationship between the theories in the previous sentence. The idea is quoted incompletely because it focuses on a learning technique that is applied to students. Students can interact in groups and are responsible for the learning that follows. Although the technique used to the original theory does not explain the Stationenlernen learning technique, it can represent that applying an appropriate learning technique can stimulate students to work in teams. In addition, the author also combines the two original theories, processing them so that they become a new idea.

Individuals change as a result of their learning experiences [29]. It found an original theory that institutions can make big changes by working together, but it's possible that the people who are most affected by these changes – students – may not be involved in the process. The sources referred to have been quoted in their entirety, and the references are explicit. This paragraph begins with a quote related to the theory of learning outcomes. The author implicitly paraphrases the meaning of the reference theory so that in detail, it can be concluded that personal changes might be determined as learning outcomes. The citation style used by the author is a partial citation, where the author determines one of the dominant and relevant words so that it is paraphrased according to the needs of the author. Related to the above theory, the author continues his quote that changes in abilities, attitudes, understandings, and self-esteem are all part of the planned transformation [30]–[33]. Based on the paraphrased theory, several original theories were found. Students' expertise in independent learning includes identifying and selecting sources, carrying out the learning process, and assessing learning outcomes. According to several evaluations, there are few evaluative methodologies available to determine how diverse school learning environments affect secondary student attitudes toward learning and their academic accomplishment. Conceptual knowledge and technical skills are separated as cognitive outputs. Conceptual knowledge is examined in all 13 publications, while technical skills are assessed in two of them [34], [35]. Conceptual knowledge referred to understanding and knowledge

of the issues covered in the laboratories. Only one article detailed the questions presented to the learners [36]. Through intrinsic goal motivation, self-esteem was revealed to predict learning techniques indirectly. The paraphrases in this discussion have quoted the source or reference in full. The sentence in this section is a continuation theory from the previous sentence and the idea is quoted partially. This fact means that the author in detail paraphrases any new findings of earlier studies related to learning outcomes. The four theories are combined into one complete sentence where there are keywords in it so that a new grouping of paraphrased ideas is found. In addition, each concept of research results is paraphrased so that it becomes a relevant reference.

It was also emphasized that learning outcomes are a description of someone's talents or skills developed in thinking, acting, and doing [37]. The original theory is created a more comprehensive evaluation system for assessing cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor activities independently. The paraphrases in this discussion have quoted the source or reference in full. In addition, the paragraph referred to is still an explanatory connection from the previous sentence. Overall, the theories quoted and paraphrased are concise and clear. In this section, there are three aspects raised by the author and paraphrased in different language styles. This situation means that the three aspects are quoted in their entirety using synonyms.

Learning outcomes are changes in abilities, attitudes and habits, comprehension, knowledge, and study that are synonymous with the categories cognitive, affective, and psychomotor as a result of the act of learning [38]. It found an original theory that psychomotor results, such as efficiency, accuracy, and response magnitude; cognitive outcomes, such as comprehension, knowledge, application, and analysis; and emotional consequences, such as satisfaction, attitude, and appreciation for the learning experience, are examples of learning outcomes [39]. This source referred to have been quoted in their entirety, and the references are clear. Furthermore, the theory in this section is also related to the previous sentence. Based on the three important aspects described previously, the writer looks for relevant data and facts to confirm the ideas of the prior theory. Facts and data obtained through relevant research results. Then the theory is quoted and paraphrased. There are many points in the original theory, but the author describes it in detail in his own words to get a concise and clear conclusion. The theory is not quoted in its entirety but focuses on important aspects of cognitive, affective, psychomotor, and German learning outcomes. Learning outcomes are said to be flawless if three factors must be met: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor [40]. For the cited theory, the original theory is found Bloom's Taxonomy is a commonly used paradigm that distinguishes three types of learning: cognitive, psychomotor, and affective [41]. The sources referred to have been quoted in their entirety, and the references are clear. To be more complete, the authors add references that are relevant to three aspects, namely cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. Overall, the author cites the theory in its entirety because these three aspects form the basis for the ideas that have been presented.

Learning outcomes are a transitional process that applies to individuals learning and is related with changes in knowledge, understanding, and competencies [42]. While the original theory is Relationships with people and the growth of selfknowledge shape an individual's self-concept. An individual's vision of the world and behavioral habits are heavily influenced by self-concept [43]. Criticks for Source integrity is the sources referred to have been quoted in their entirety, and the references are clear. Implicitly the meaning of the original theory is paraphrased by the author by linking the formation of self-concept through collaboration with others, development of knowledge, and the influence of perceptions on the environment and behavior of role models. Thus, paraphrasing does not represent the whole theory, so some parts are omitted. When a person has completed the learning process, their behavior will transform. Modifications can be seen in the following ways: Knowledge, Cognitive skills, Motor skills, Affective learning outcomes, and Communicative learning outcomes [44]. Related to the above theory, the author continues his quote that when a person has completed the learning process, their behavior will transform. Modifications can be seen in the following ways: knowledge, cognitive skills, motor skills, affective learning outcomes, and communicative learning outcomes [44]. The original theory is cognitive learning outcomes are further classified as knowledge and cognitive skills, physical abilities, emotional learning outcomes, and communicative learning outcomes [45]. The sources referred to have been quoted in their entirety, and the references are clear. In this paragraph, the author cites many relevant theories relating to three aspects, namely cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. Each element is described in detail, supported by data and facts from research results and opinions from experts so that the ideas conveyed by the author are scientifically acceptable. In addition, the author uses the style of citing theory in its entirety and paraphrased briefly and clearly according to the author's needs.

The results of teaching and learning German are the modifications in knowledge, understanding, and attitudes that students experience [46]. The theory cited by the author refers to a conclusion. If it is related to the original theory in the article quoted by the author, namely code-switches (CS) gives a unique perspective into the structural effects of language encounter,"[47]. The use of event related potentials (ERP) to examine CS processing can give information regarding the effects of various sorts of language contact scenarios, as

well as the unique cognitive processes at work in bilingualism. The sources referred to have been quoted incompletely, but the references are clear. The author quotes and paraphrases this theory to conclude the overall idea that has been conveyed previously related to learning outcomes. In this section, the author only cites related situations in language learning to stimulate one's cognitive processes to improve learning outcomes. The paraphrased theory is incomplete. This fact means that it only focuses on points that are relevant to the research problem.

4. CONCLUSION

In general, reference sources are given academic awards by being quoted in their entirety. However, some reference sources are still less relevant to the research problem, and there are slight errors in citing reference sources originating from the same author. As a whole, the quotation or paraphrase has taken into account the integrity of the meaning with several techniques, namely the complete and partial techniques. Whole in the sense that the theory is paraphrased without losing the meaning. At the same time, the partial is divided into two, namely: i) Paraphrasing tends to quote important aspects according to the needs and objectives of the writing; ii) Combining several theories and then processing them briefly and clearly to become a new idea. This review is a reference and input for writers to remain professional in citing sources and paraphrasing theories, ideas, or ideas in writing scientific articles to avoid plagiarism.

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REFERENCES

- [1] E. C. Wenno and K. Karuna, "Hots (High Order Thinking Skill) In German Language Test (in Indonesian)," *J-EDU: Journal Erfolgreicher Deutschunterricht*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 17–23, 2021, doi: 10.30598/J-EDU.1.1.17-23.
- [2] D. Tong *et al.*, "Critical thinking and regional gray matter volume interact to predict representation connection in scientific problem solving," *Experimental Brain Research*, vol. 237, no. 8, pp. 2035–2044, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s00221-019-05517-y.
- [3] M. C. Reale, D. M. Riche, B. A. Witt, W. L. Baker, and M. J. Peeters, "Development of critical thinking in health professions education: A meta-analysis of longitudinal studies," *Currents in Pharmacy Teaching and Learning*, vol. 10, no. 7, pp. 826–833, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cptl.2018.04.019.
- [4] A. Y. Gasparyan, B. Nurmashv, B. Seksenbayev, V. I. Trukhachev, E. I. Kostyukova, and G. D. Kitas, "Plagiarism in the Context of Education and Evolving Detection Strategies," *Journal of Korean Medical Science*, vol. 32, no. 8, pp. 1220–1227, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.3346/jkms.2017.32.8.1220.
- [5] A. Wibowo, "Preventing and tackling plagiarism in the world of education (in Indonesian)," *Kesmas: Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat Nasional (National Public Health Journal)*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 195–200, 2012, doi: 10.21109/kesmas.v6i5.84.
- [6] Sukaesih, "Plagiarism Problems in Qualitative Research in Indonesia (in Indonesian)," *Politik Indonesia*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 210–218, 2018, doi: 10.35706/jpi.v3i1.1424.
- [7] M. A. Shadiqi, "Understanding and Preventing Plagiarism Behavior in Scientific Writing (in Indonesian)," *Buletin Psikologi*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 30–42, 2019, doi: 10.22146/buletinpsikologi.43058.
- [8] A. R. Memon, "Similarity and Plagiarism in Scholarly Journal Submissions: Bringing Clarity to the Concept for Authors, Reviewers and Editors," *Journal of Korean Medical Science*, vol. 35, no. 27, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.3346/jkms.2020.35.e217.
- [9] R. A. Harris, *Using Sources Effectively: Strengthening Your Writing and Avoiding Plagiarism*, Fourth Ed. New York: Roudledge, Taylor and Francis, 2017.
- [10] M. F. Abad-García, "El plagio y las revistas depredadoras como amenaza a la integridad científica," *Anales de Pediatría*, vol. 90, no. 1, pp. 57.e1-57.e8, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.anpedi.2018.11.003.
- [11] J. W. Creswell, *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*, Fifth. Singapore: SAGE Publications Inc, 2018.
- [12] S. J. Litaly and H. Serpara, "Stationenlernen Learning Technique and German Language Learning Outcomes.," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 421–426, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v9i2.20467.
- [13] A. Abduh and R. Rosmaladewi, "Language policy, identity, and bilingual education in Indonesia: A historical overview," vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 219–227, 2019, doi: 10.18355/XL.2019.12.01.17.
- [14] S. Dardjowidjojo, "Strategies for a successful national language policy: The Indonesian case," *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, vol. 130, no. 1, pp. 35–48, 1998, doi: 10.1515/ijsl.1998.130.35.
- [15] S. U. Nababan, *Discourse Analysis and Language Teaching (in Indonesian)*, Jakarta: IKIP Jakarta, 1999.
- [16] S. Turner and P. Allen, "Chinese Indonesians in a rapidly changing nation: Pressures of ethnicity and identity," *Asia pacific viewpoint*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 112–127, 2007, doi: 10.1111/j.1467-8373.2007.00334.x.
- [17] B. Gasperschitz, S. Hecht, and G. Piccardo, "Was ist los in Hauptstraße 117?," *Fascicolo di Supporto*, Genova, 2007.
- [18] B. Hufeisen, "Krumm, Hans-Jürgen (Hg.) (1999), Sprachen-Brücken über Grenzen. Deutsch als Fremdsprache in Mittel- und Osteuropa. Dokumentation der Wiener Konferenz 17.-21.2. 1998," *Zeitschrift für Interkulturellen Fremdsprachenunterricht*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2000.
- [19] E. Peters, "Learning German formulaic sequences: The effect of two attention-drawing techniques," *The Language Learning Journal*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 65–79, 2012, doi: 10.1080/09571736.2012.658224.
- [20] L. Wickramanayake and S. Muhammad Jika, "Social media use by undergraduate students of education in Nigeria: a survey," *The*

- Electronic Library*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 21–37, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1108/EL-01-2017-0023.
- [21] D. H. Wartono and J. R. B. Nilasari, “Real-virtual monte carlo simulation on impulse-momentum and collisions,” *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 7–14, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v13.i1.pp7-14.
- [22] J. Redmann, “An interactive reading journal for all levels of the foreign language curriculum,” *Foreign Language Annals*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 484–492, 2005, doi: 10.1111/j.1944-9720.2005.tb02515.x.
- [23] J. Redmann, “Stationenlernen: A student-centered approach to working with foreign language texts,” *Die Unterrichtspraxis/Teaching German*, pp. 135–142, 2005, doi: 10.1111/j.1756-1221.2005.tb00051.x.
- [24] J. Handrich and R. Vandenhouten, “Erweiterung eines landmarkenbasierten Innenraumortungsverfahrens für Mobilgeräte mit ARCore,” *Wissenschaftliche Beiträge / Technische Hochschule Wildau*, vol. 23, pp. 27–32, 2019, doi: 10.15771/0949-8214_2019_4.
- [25] M. Selkrig and (Ron) Kim Keamy, “Creative pedagogy: a case for teachers’ creative learning being at the centre,” *Teaching Education*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 317–332, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1080/10476210.2017.1296829.
- [26] D. Davies, D. Jindal-Snape, C. Collier, R. Digby, P. Hay, and A. Howe, “Creative learning environments in education—A systematic literature review,” *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, vol. 8, pp. 80–91, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.tsc.2012.07.004.
- [27] M. Leasa, Y. L. Sanabuky, J. R. Batlolona, and J. J. Enriquez, “Jigsaw in teaching circulatory system: a learning activity on elementary science classroom,” *Biosfer*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 122–134, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.21009/biosferjpb.v12n2.122-134.
- [28] M. Norhailawati *et al.*, “The power of social networking sites: Student involvement toward education,” *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 549–556, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v8i3.20352.
- [29] T. Jorre de St Jorre and B. Oliver, “Want students to engage? Contextualise graduate learning outcomes and assess for employability,” *Higher Education Research & Development*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 44–57, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1080/07294360.2017.1339183.
- [30] A. S. Kastenmeier *et al.*, “Individual learning plans foster self-directed learning skills and contribute to improved educational outcomes in the surgery clerkship,” *The American Journal of Surgery*, vol. 216, no. 1, pp. 160–166, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.amjsurg.2018.01.023.
- [31] T. Byers, W. Imms, and E. Hartnell-Young, “Comparative analysis of the impact of traditional versus innovative learning environment on student attitudes and learning outcomes,” *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, vol. 58, pp. 167–177, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.stueduc.2018.07.003.
- [32] L. S. Post, P. Guo, N. Saab, and W. Admiraal, “Effects of remote labs on cognitive, behavioral, and affective learning outcomes in higher education,” *Computers & Education*, vol. 140, p. 103596, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103596.
- [33] C. M. Kokkinos and I. Voulgaridou, “Motivational beliefs as mediators in the association between perceived scholastic competence, self-esteem and learning strategies among Greek secondary school students,” *Educational Psychology*, vol. 38, no. 6, pp. 753–771, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1080/01443410.2018.1456651.
- [34] X. Chen and H. Gao, “A Remote PLC Laboratory Design and Realization,” *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 31, pp. 1168–1172, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.proeng.2012.01.1158.
- [35] L. Fiore and G. Ratti, “Remote laboratory and animal behaviour: An interactive open field system,” *Computers & Education*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 1299–1307, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2006.02.005.
- [36] M. Sauter, D. H. Uttal, D. N. Rapp, M. Downing, and K. Jona, “Getting real: the authenticity of remote labs and simulations for science learning,” *Distance Education*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 37–47, May 2013, doi: 10.1080/01587919.2013.770431.
- [37] G. Kasilingam and E. Chinnavan, “Assessment of learning domains to improve student’s learning in higher education,” *Journal of Young Pharmacists*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2014, doi: 10.5530/jyp.2014.1.5.
- [38] C. L. Huang, Y. F. Luo, S. C. Yang, C. M. Lu, and A.-S. Chen, “Influence of Students’ Learning Style, Sense of Presence, and Cognitive Load on Learning Outcomes in an Immersive Virtual Reality Learning Environment,” *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 596–615, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1177/0735633119867422.
- [39] R. SHARDA *et al.*, “Foundation for the Study of Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning Requiring Immersive Presence,” *Journal of Management Information Systems*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 31–64, Mar. 2004, doi: 10.1080/07421222.2004.11045780.
- [40] A. J. Muzyk *et al.*, “Utilizing Bloom’s taxonomy to design a substance use disorders course for health professions students,” *Substance Abuse*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 348–353, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1080/08897077.2018.1436634.
- [41] B. S. Bloom, *Taxonomy of educational objectives, handbook I: The cognitive domain*. New York: David McKay Co Inc., 1956.
- [42] M. A. B. Delcourt, D. G. Cornell, and M. D. Goldberg, “Cognitive and Affective Learning Outcomes of Gifted Elementary School Students,” *Gifted Child Quarterly*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 359–381, Jan. 2007, doi: 10.1177/0016986207306320.
- [43] M. P. Driscoll and K. J. Burner, *Psychology of learning for instruction*. Boston: Pearson Allyn and Bacon, 2005.
- [44] T. M. Connolly, E. A. Boyle, E. MacArthur, T. Hainey, and J. M. Boyle, “A systematic literature review of empirical evidence on computer games and serious games,” *Computers & Education*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 661–686, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2012.03.004.
- [45] P. Wouters, E. D. Van der Spek, and H. Van Oostendorp, “Current practices in serious game research: A review from a learning outcomes perspective,” *Games-based learning advancements for multi-sensory human computer interfaces: techniques and effective practices*, pp. 232–250, 2009.
- [46] E. Ruigendijk, G. Hentschel, and J. P. Zeller, “How L2-learners’ brains react to code-switches: An ERP study with Russian learners of German,” *Second Language Research*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 197–223, Nov. 2015, doi: 10.1177/0267658315614614.
- [47] B. E. Bullock and A. J. E. Toribio, *Themes in the study of code-switching. The Cambridge handbook of linguistic code-switching*. Cambridge University Press, 2009.

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